

Implementation of the Merdeka Program as Efforts to Improve Competitive Village Economic Development: (A Case Study of the Implementation of the UTS Assisted Village Merdeka Program in 19 Villages in Sumbawa Regency)

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ABSTRACT : This study aims to determine the implementation of the merdeka program as an effort to improve village economic development in 19 assisted villages in the Sumbawa Regency Region and the factors that influence the implementation of the merdeka program. The theoretical approach used to analyze it is the implementation of Public policy according to George C. Edward III's model, namely analysis through four factors that influence the success or failure of implementing a policy, namely factors of resources, communication, disposition and bureaucratic structure.

This research is a type of applied research or field research with a qualitative approach. The results show that the implementation of the merdeka program at the Sumbawa University of Technology has been carried out by fulfilling the indicator criteria for developing villages by using aspects of communication, resources, attitudes and bureaucratic structure which is indicated by the formation of an merdeka program implementing team from the Vice Chancellor for Research and Innovation which in this case through the Directorate of Community Service. Then the factors that influence the success of the implementation of the Merdeka Program at the Sumbawa University of Technology, namely there is a sense of ownership by stakeholders in developing villages in Sumbawa Regency, the active role of village heads in developing villages to improve village economic development through the Merdeka Program and the emergence of innovation and development. the creativity of the Sumbawa University of Technology students in growing and designing village products to be used as the village's flagship product in order to increase the income of the village community.

KEYWORDS - Implementation of the Sumbawa University of Technology merdeka program.

I. INTRODUCTION

PERHEPI [10], reports on the number of government projects/programs that have been carried out to encourage the economic development of rural communities. The project/program is carried out by each department or between departments. In general, the projects that are rolled out are still in the generation of providing physical assistance to the community. Either in the form of irrigation facilities, assistance for agricultural crops, pump machines, construction of clean water facilities and so on. In fact, when the project

ends, the output of the project is no longer functional or even lost. Several factors that influence the failure of the project include: (1) inaccuracy between community needs and the assistance provided (2) the project package is not equipped with supporting skills (3) there is no planned monitoring activity (4) there are no institutions in community level continuing the project. One of the interesting programs to study related to encouraging rural economic development is the implementation of the Merdeka program policies. What is meant by Program implementation in this case as stated by Solikhin Abdul Wahab in his book entitled Policy Analysis: from the Formulation of State Policy Implementation are as follows: "Implementation are actions taken by individuals or officials government or private groups that are directed to achieve the goals that have been outlined in policy decisions" [16].

The merdeka program is a real form of implementation of the new curriculum direction that was initiated today with the name Campus Merdeka by the Minister of Education and Culture on January 24, 2020. The program is run by the Sumbawa University of Technology. according to the needs of each university. The policy involves students and the role of supervisors to actively participate in regional development. One of the activities that can be carried out by students and supervisors is to be involved in fostered village projects. The broad description of the objectives of the assisted village activities consists of five activities, three of which are developing the local potential of the village, making the village community independent and competitive and these activities must prioritize the participation of the entire community and village officials. From a series of village development activities, a mapping of the potential of villages that will become the target of village development is carried out, while the number of targeted villages consists of 19 villages in Sumbawa Regency. 19 This Sumbawaa is the result of recommendations from parties such as the Regional Government, Sumbawa DPRD and UTS as listed in the table below.

TABLE 1: Number of Merdeka Program Villages

No.	Village
1.	Lito
2.	Semamung
3.	Batu Tering
4.	Marga Karya
5.	Sebasang
6.	Batu bulan
7.	Lamenta
8.	Jontang
9.	Boal
10.	Selante
11.	Usar
12.	Teluj Santong
13.	Bungin
14.	Luar
15.	Labu Burung
16.	Pulau Kaung
17.	Tarusa
18.	Leseng
19.	Perung

Source: Sumbawa University of Technology (UTS)

The Independent Village Development Program is one of UTS' intellectual products and the only one in Indonesia, which is built from program indicators, namely the Village Development Indicator with the Main programs: Digital Village, OVOP (One Village One Product), Cultural Village, Tourism Village and the Administrative Neat Village. The achievement of these indicators is assessed based on the Pre Test and Post Test scores of the Merdeka Program, Monitoring and Evaluation Results during the Program Period, Publications and IPR, and others. In the implementation of the merdeka program in 2020, the allocation of grant funds disbursed from Stakeholders through the Sumbawa University of Technology in the form of Regional Incentive Funds of Rp. 777,945,8000, allocated a budget of Rp. 40,925,500 to 18 villages, one village received as much as Rp. 41,286,800,-. With the disbursement of these funds, what needs to be considered is the extent to which the optimal implementation level of the program is, therefore this research will raise how the implementation of the guided village merdeka program has been after the village grant funds have been disbursed as an effort to increase the competitive economic development of the village and will also address the problem -what factors influence the implementation of the assisted village merdeka program. The approach used in analyzing the implementation of program policies regarding the merdeka program is the theory put forward by George C. Edward III. Where implementation can start from abstract conditions and a question about whether the conditions for policy implementation can be successful, according to George C.Edward III there are four variables in public policy, namely Communication (communications), Resources (resources), Attitudes (dispositions or attitudes) and Structural bureaucracy (bureueratic structure). The purpose to be achieved in this research is to know and analyze:

- a. Analyzing and describing the implementation of the guided merdeka program in 19 assisted villages in Sumbawa Regency as an effort to increase competitive village economic development.
- b. Identifying the factors that influence the implementation of the merdeka program as an effort to increase competitive village economic development.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Public Policy Implementation Theory

The study of the implementation of public policy is a study of the implementation of a government policy. After a policy is formulated and approved, the next step is how to make the policy achieve its objectives. According to Nugroho [9] in his book Public Policy, Formulation, Implementation, and Evaluation in principle is a way for a policy to achieve its objectives. As for implementing public policies in the form of programs or through policy formulation derivatives or derivatives of these public policies. According to George C Edwards III in Yulianto Kadji [18], to answer the possibilities mentioned above, there are four factors that work simultaneously and interact with each other to help and hinder policy implementation, so the ideal approach is to reflect this complexity with the four these factors, namely: "Communication, resources, dispositions or attitudes, and bureaucratic structure".

Figure 1: Policy Implementation Model according to Edwards III

In the policy implementation process, communication plays an important role because implementers must know what they are going to do. The order to implement the policy must be passed on to the implementer in a precise and consistent manner. Lack of resources will result in ineffective policy implementation. The disposition or attitude of the implementer is defined as the desire and agreement among the implementers to

implement the policy. If the implementation of the policy will be carried out effectively, then the implementor not only knows what they have to do and has the ability to implement it, but the implementor must also have the desire to implement the policy. Finally, the bureaucratic structure has an impact on implementation in the sense that the implementation will not succeed if there are deficiencies in the bureaucratic structure.

Program Merdeka

The Merdeka Program is a concrete implementation of the direction of the new curriculum which is currently being initiated under the name Campus Merdeka by the Minister of Education and Culture on January 24, 2020. This curriculum has four policy packages as its foundation, one of which is the right to study for three semesters outside the study program (Prodi).) for students. The merdeka program that is the focus of this research is the thematic village development program/KKN.

Village Development

Based on the opinion of Supriyatna [11], that rural community development can be viewed from the systems approach, methods and development movements carried out by the community together with the government in order to improve the quality of life and life as a whole, especially in overcoming poverty, underdevelopment and ignorance of the population in an area or rural enclave. The general principles of village development including rural community development include: the principles of sustainable, integral, and dynamic development. However, the principles of rural community development are need-oriented, participation, integration, sustainability, harmony, self-sufficiency/independence and regeneration.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This research includes field research, namely research carried out in the field in the real world [7]. The essence of field research is research conducted by identifying data sourced from the research location or field. The data were obtained from locations in 19 villages in Sumbawa district. While the nature of this writing is qualitative descriptive analysis, which explains that qualitative research is research to describe and analyze phenomena, events, social activities, beliefs, perceptions, thoughts individually and in groups [6]. The notion of qualitative methods according to Bogdan and Taylor in Moleong, [8] defines qualitative methods as research procedures that produce descriptive data in the form of written or spoken words from people and observable behavior. So this research was conducted by describing the implementation of the independence program for local economic development as an effort to increase village competitiveness and describing several factors that influence the implementation of the merdeka program activities that are currently ending. Research with a qualitative approach emphasizes the analysis on the process of inductive inference and analysis of the dynamics of the pattern of relationships/relationships between observed phenomena using scientific methods.

Data was collected by using purposive sampling technique. According to Sugiyono [13] purposive sampling is a sampling technique with certain considerations. In this study, the subjects who will be interviewed as key informants include the person in charge of the merdeka program for the purpose of developing the village, among others.

- a. Rector of the Sumbawa University of Technology
- b. Leader of WRIII for Research and Innovation, Sumbawa University of Technology
- c. Chairman of the Sumbawa Regency DPRD
- d. Head of the Sumbawa Regency DPM Service
- e. Sumbawa Regency Bappeda
- f. Village head

In accordance with the qualitative approach, the data collection techniques used by researchers in this study include: *Interview, Observation and Documentation*.

Validation

According to Moleong [8], "Triangulation is a technique for checking the validity of data that utilizes something other than the data for checking purposes or as a comparison against the data". To validate the data, researchers used data triangulation and method triangulation. Where data triangulation is used to collect similar data using a variety of different data sources. While the triangulation method is used to compare the data from interviews, namely comparing what is in the document with the results of observations and comparing the results of interviews with the contents of related documents.

Data Analysis

To support the analysis of the data used in the study, the researcher used the income of HB Sutopo [2] who quoted the opinion of Miles & Huberman: "There are three main components that researchers must really understand, namely (1) data reduction, (2) display data, (3) decision making or verification.

IV. RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

1. Research Findings

A. *Mechanims and Form of Policy Support for The Merdeka Program At The Sumbawa University Of Technology.*

In its implementation, the merdeka Program mechanism will be regulated by the Directorate of Community Service under the coordination of the Vice Chancellor for Research and Innovation. Simply put, the Merdeka Program is not much different from the KKN in general in the community, so the implementation mechanism is not much different. Students must be accompanied by accompanying lecturers, register, receive program briefing, find destination villages, develop relevant programs and start building villages with the community. The support for the form of support for the merdeka program policy carried out by the Sumbawa University of Technology as stated by the Deputy Chancellor 3 UTS Khotibul Umam, S.Si., M.Sc: "*In terms of the form of support for the Merdeka Program, the Deputy Rector 3 of UTS began to communicate with stakeholders such as Pemdes, Sumbawa Regency DPRD, Sumbawa Regency DPM and Sumbawa Regency Bappeda then developed a joint concept in developing villages. Then we consistently carry out both formal and informal communication regarding matters relating to any additional concepts in developing the village (Khotibul Umam, S.Si., M.Sc .27 April 2021)*".

The same thing was stated by the Vice Rector 4 of UTS regarding the support of the Merdeka Program at UTS: "*From the beginning the Warek 4 made sure to back up all parties involved because of this concept (the independence program) starting from the Warek 3 and Warek 4 ensuring all parties such as the Village Government, DPM Sumbawa Regency, Sumbawa Regency DPRD and Bappeda are involved in implementing the independence program at UTS. Then the Warek 4 provides human resources and intensively builds communication with all parties involved, either communicating informally or formally to related parties who support the merdeka program. (Vice Rector 4 UTS, 28 April 2021)*".

Based on the in-depth study described in this section, the authors arrive at a construction of understanding that the mechanism and support for the implementation of the Merdeka Program at the Sumbawa University of Technology has been going well. Starting from building a concept and building collaborative communication and engagement with related parties such as the Village Government, Sumbawa Regency DPRD, Sumbawa Regency DPM and Sumbawa Regency Bappeda.

B. *Socialization And Coordination Of The Implementation Of The Merdeka Program*

Elements of socialization and coordination are important in the implementation of the independent village development program in order to maintain certainty and consistency in a work program. Delivery of

merdeka program activities starts from internal (Sumwawa Technological University) to external parties (stakeholders) if it can be communicated either through formal or informal as stated by UTS Deputy Chancellor 3 Khotibul Umam, S.Si., M.Sc: *"We build communication so far through information and formal. As for formally, we invited stakeholders (Bappeda Sumbawa Regency, DPRD Sumbawa Regency, Sumbawa Regency DPM and Sumbawa Regency Pemdes) in an official forum to discuss the concept of an independent program to build villages in Sumbawa Regency. From this discussion we get the solution of the problem to be solved together. Meanwhile, informally, we and stakeholders chatted casually at the Roakawa cafe to discuss the follow-up to the independent village development program. (Khotibul Umam, S.Si., M.Sc. 27 April 2021)"*.

The form of socialization support and coordination of stakeholders for the implementation of the merdeka program to build villages as carried out by the Head of the Sumbawa Regency Community Empowerment Service from the results of the interview he stated that *"Because this independence program is aimed at empowering villages, from our side with the Pemdes open communication space through The Village Head forum group with the aim of maintaining communication as well as creating a space for socialization and coordination between DPM and Pemdes related to various information and problems faced by villages, especially socialization information related to the independent program to build villages. (Head of the Sumbawa District DPM Service, 28 April 2021)"*.

Regarding the above, the head of the Sumbawa Regency DPRD also gave a statement regarding the socialization and coordination of the implementation of the merdeka program so far. He stated that *"the concept of building socialization and coordination of the implementation of the merdeka program has been going well, whether it is through formal or informal because the Sumbawa University of Technology as the executor of this independence program through the Vice Chancellor 4 always maintains communication between the university and stakeholders starting from the planning stage, implementation and evaluation of this volume one independence program. (Chairman of the Sumbawa Regency DPRD April 29, 2021)"*.

C. Scope Of Monitoring Indicators For The Implementation Of The Merdeka program.

From the research findings, there are several aspects of the scope of indicators for monitoring the implementation of the merdeka program, both from the Sumbawa University of Technology and from the stakeholders included in the results of the interviews. As for the University, what was conveyed by Warek 4 Khotibul Umam, S.Si., M.Sc revealed that *"From the community service side, there are two mechanisms that are used as indicators for the implementation of the merdeka program, namely the pretest and posttest mechanisms. For the pretest itself, it explores related things about villages that refer to the Development Village Index it aims to find out how far the village level is, whether at the level of lagging, developing or advanced. Then for the post-test, it explores the increase in the village level and the obstacles faced by the village. Then the indicators used are also about the success of the village seen from the results of the products produced by the village during the merdeka program, this is reflected in the one village one product indicator. Then for the stakeholders, we invite them to see the ongoing merdeka program process and see the results of the merdeka program activities. (Khotibul Umam, S.Si., M.Sc. 27 April 2021)"*.

Then the same statement was expressed by Warek 4 regarding indicators for monitoring the implementation of the merdeka program stating that *"we invite all parties, both universities and stakeholders (Sumbawa Regency DPRD, Sumbawa Bappeda, Sumbawa DPM and Pemdes) in the field to see the ongoing merdeka program process with the aim of together we plan this program and evaluate it together so that we can solve the shortcomings together in the future (Warek 4 UTS, 28 April 2021)"*.

Meanwhile, the stakeholder stated about the implementation of the monitoring indicators for the merdeka program so far that *"the emergence of community empowerment in accordance with the potential of the village and the introduction of several technologies to facilitate the production process in order to create a one product one village has made us participate in the field to see the ongoing process. with the Sumbawa University of Technology and other stakeholders. So from monitoring the merdeka program, we can see which ones are lacking to be used as input in the future (Head of the Sumbawa Regency DPM Service, 28 April 2021)"*.

D. Strategi for The Implementation Of The Merdeka Program At The Sumbawa University Of Technology.

To carry out the merdeka program, a mature strategy is needed to achieve the targets to be achieved starting from a careful planning to the implementation and evaluation of the merdeka program. The merdeka program as stated by Khotibul Umam, S.Si., M.Sc is "we from the Warek 3 party build communication between stakeholders such as the village government, Sumbawa Regency DPRD, Bappeda, Sumbawa Regency DPM Service and the University itself to work together discusses related to the merdeka program, starting from the funds that will be prepared in the merdeka program to the implementation of the budget that is adjusted to the merdeka program plan as the result of a mutual agreement. (Khotibul Umam, S.Si., M.Sc. 27 April 2021)".

From the presentation of the strategy for implementing the merdeka program carried out by the Sumbawa University of Technology, the stakeholder parties such as the Sumbawa DPRD and the Sumbawa Regency Bappeda revealed that "building joint communication is a good strategy in involving all elements in the independence program so that we will find out what priorities will be implemented to develop the village so that the DPRD Kab. Sumbawa can definitely lock the budget for the independence program that is in accordance with political priorities." (Chairman of the Sumbawa Regency DPRD 29 April 2021)". The same thing was conveyed by the Head of Bappeda Kab. Sumbawa regarding the strategy for implementing the Merdeka Program for this first stage, namely "The Sumbawa University of Technology with other stakeholders needs to build a communication in preparation for the implementation of the independence program so that we feel we have the same ownership of the merdeka program. This is for Bappeda itself to have several interests in the merdeka program, including planning in developing villages which is included in the program every year. With this merdeka program, the Sumbawa Regency government will greatly assist in the village development program". Head of Bappeda Kab. Sumbawa, 30 April 2021).

E. Problems During The Implementation Of The Merdeka Program.

From the research findings in the process of implementing the merdeka Program, several problems were found in the implementation of the merdeka program which were described by the Warek 4 Khotibul Umam, S.Si., M.Sc, namely "During the process of the journey of this merdeka program, we found several problems that we might divide into: two, namely internal and external problems. For internal problems, namely the problem of finding free time with stakeholders to discuss the merdeka program intensely as well as financial problems in the implementation of the merdeka program, in this case we always communicate with stakeholders to encourage commitment from the beginning so that it can always run smoothly. Then in terms of lectures, namely how the cooperation of Warek 1 with Warek 3 in ensuring the curriculum runs smoothly in the village. And for external problems that arise from the village, for example in the form of a misunderstanding on the part of the community regarding some student problems in carrying out activities during the corona pandemic." (Khotibul Umam, S.Si., M.Sc. 27 April 2021)".

From the explanation given by Warek 3 above, the same thing was also conveyed by Warek 1 he said "that related to problems during the implementation of this merdeka program, Warek 1 ensures that the curriculum in each study program can run well as long as the independence program runs". (Abdul Hadil Ilman, M.P.P, April 25, 2021)".

The responses from several stakeholders to problems during the implementation of the merdeka program such as the Head of DPM Kab. Sumbawa he said "that finding free time for intense communication regarding the implementation and development of the merdeka program still has to be seriously considered in order to maintain a sense of commitment to the togetherness of implementing the merdeka program". (Head of the Sumbawa District DPM Service, 28 April 2021)".

F. Troubleshooting their Merdeka Program

Regarding the problems faced during the implementation of the merdeka program, it is necessary to take some appropriate steps for the smooth implementation of the merdeka program and become material for the improvement of the merdeka program for the next stage. The solution to the problems of the merdeka program

can be done in several ways, as stated by Warek 3, namely "we look for the root of the problem first then we communicate and coordinate with stakeholders then we go down to the villages to find out the problem. and invites to communicate in order to solve the problem, it is for external problems. For internal problems, we continue to build smooth communication with stakeholders regarding the merdeka program funds so that they can be formulated and used as a mainstay program in developing villages". (Khotibul Umam, S.Si., M.Sc. 27 April 2021)".

The Vice Rector 4 also expressed the same response regarding the resolution of problems both external and internal. Specifically for internal problems, Warek 4 revealed that "how to maintain effective and sustainable communication with stakeholders in order to keep this merdeka program running sustainably in developing villages, especially related to the independence program budget funds, so that it can be used as a mainstay program for local governments in developing villages. sustainability through the merdeka program". (Warek 4 UTS, 28 April 2021)".

G. The Sustainability Of The Merdeka Program

At the end of the implementation of the First Phase of the Merdeka Program, a meaningful continuation of the program is needed. So that the results of the first phase of the program can continue in the second phase of the merdeka program, if the products produced in the first phase of the merdeka program can be developed in the second phase of the merdeka program, as stated by Warek 3 that "achievement of the results of the first phase of the merdeka program can be continued in the second phase of the independence program. both the merdeka program, such as indicators of the achievement of the one village one product merdeka program, how the superior village products that have been made and packaged to be exhibited at the end of the merdeka program, can be made a further concept regarding the marketing of the superior product which will be designed and applied in the second phase of the program. independence and the most important thing is the certainty of commitment from stakeholders for the smooth running of the merdeka program such as guaranteeing the budget". (Khotibul Umam, S.Si., M.Sc. 27 April 2021)".

In the explanation given by Vice Rector 4 regarding the sustainability of the merdeka program, he explained that "we and the stakeholders will ensure the sustainability of this independence program, one form of sustainability commitment from the stakeholders, one of which is asking for the commitment of the Sumbawa Regency Government to include this merdeka program at the ceiling. the annual budget as part of the Sumbawa Regency village development program". (Warek 4 UTS, 28 April 2021)".

Discussion

Independence Program Policy at Sumbawa University of Technology.

In the policy aspect of the independence program at the Sumbawa University of Technology which was implemented in 2020 in Sumbawa Regency in 19 villages, the issues raised were building villages for community welfare which focused on increasing the Village Development Indicators on the development of physical and non-physical potential (HR.) or in terms of increasing intellectual capital (human capital, social capital, structural capital) in the target village. This is in line with the directives of the Regional Government, DPRD and other elements who both want to increase the value and capitalization of the existing natural resources in these villages. The target of the merdeka program is to look at the potential of the village as measured by the One Village One product, Digital Village, Cultural Village, Tourism Village and Administrative Neat Village. The main program targets are the Digital Village and One Village One Product and the additional programs are the Cultural Village, Administrative Neat Village and Tourism Village. From the results of the implementation of the merdeka program at the Sumbawa University of Technology in 2020, it is necessary to evaluate the implementation of the program to see how far the results have been achieved so far so that they can be used as material for review of decision making for the next stage of the merdeka program and try to find obstacles and impetus for implementing the merdeka program . To see the achievement of the implementation of the independence program, the research uses four indicators in George C.Edward III's theory:

Communications

Communication has an important role for the ongoing coordination in the implementation of a policy. Communication is a process of coordination and integration of various functions that exist in each part of the structure of policy implementation in order to obtain similarities and alignment of actions and perceptions from policy implementing officials to conform to the provisions and objectives of the policy. According to Edward III, there are three indicators that can be used to measure the success of communication variables, which consist of: transmission or distribution of communication, clarity of communication and consistency of communication. According to DB Cutis 1992 [17] is the ability to communicate showing sending messages clearly, humanely and efficiently and receive messages accurately.

From the above understanding, it is clear that before the implementation of the Sumbawa University of Technology program, it is necessary to communicate with stakeholders with the aim of avoiding misunderstandings and establishing good coordination. This is as stated by Warek 4 as the bridge between the implementation of this merdeka program and the stakeholders. According to Warek 4 that *"from the beginning the concept of the merdeka e program was created, it involved stakeholders including: DPRD Sumbawa Regency, Sumbawa Regency Government, Sumbawa Regency DPM and Village Heads to discuss the concept of problems to be solved in the village through the merdeka program, although not a few We deny that the communication that we have built so far, both informally and formally, is sometimes constrained by the free time that stakeholders have in arranging meeting schedules due to their busy lives". Warek 4 UTS, 28 April 2021)*".

This is in line with what was expressed by one of the village heads, namely the village head of Alas who stated that *"communication so far has almost gone well, whether it is through formal and informal activities related to developing villages through the merdeka program, it's just that the time owned by the stakeholders must be adjusted. with their respective work schedules. (Head of Alas Luar Village, 3 May 2021)"*.

The above is also reinforced by the results of Ilham's research [5] with the title "implementation of local government policies in basic public services in the social sector in the city of Makassar" regarding the suitability of the George C Edward III Model. The conformity in question is seen through the important role of communication in the form of socialization, involvement of parties in maintaining communication on the implementation of government policies. So it seems that there will be consistent coordination until the end of the implementation of local government policy programs.

Resources

George Edward III suggests that the resource factor is really significant to the policy implementation process. According to him, the resource factors include physical resources (facilities), staff resources (number and competencies), information resources and authority resources (Authority). Based on the results of an interview with the Chancellor of the Sumbawa University of Technology that *"to achieve optimal results in the implementation of this merdeka program, we always monitor from the warek 3 reports regarding the implementation of this merdeka program and we also go into the field with stakeholders to ensure the achievement of the merdeka program implementation so far." (Khairul Hudaya.Ph.d, 08 May 2021)"*.

The statement by the Chancellor of the Sumbawa University of Technology is also in line with the Warek 3's delivery during the interview process, namely *"to improve the perfect results we send our staff to go through pre-test and post-test on the activities of the merdeka program so far to find out the achievements that have been drawn and what obstacles are found. We will use this field as input for the next phase of the merdeka program." (Khotibul Umam, S.Si., M.Sc. 27 April 2021)"*.

As stated by Professor Haedar Akib, State University of Makassar [3], that resource and compliance factors in the implementation of program policies are very important in realizing the implementation of program policies in accordance with the plan.

Attitudes

The attitude of the implementer is the third important factor in the process of implementing public policy. If policy implementation is expected to be effective, then policy implementers not only know what must be done and have the capability to implement it, but they must also have the desire and tendency to have a positive attitude to implement the policy. As also stated by Subarsono [12] that disposition or commitment is a factor that comes from within the individual of each program implementing staff in the form of willingness or willingness of implementing staff to carry out their duties and obligations in implementing the program as well as possible in accordance with the guidelines and instructions provided. has been established. If the implementor has a good disposition, then he will be able to carry out the policy well as desired by the policy maker. However, when the implementor has a different attitude or perspective from the policy maker, the policy implementation process will also be ineffective.

The willingness of these implementers is influenced by three elements as follows: first is their cognition (level of knowledge and understanding) of the policy; second, the direction of their response to the policy; third, the intensity of their response to the policy. If these three things show a positive direction, the level of willingness to implement policies will be high, and vice versa [1].

The implementation team of the Sumbawa University of Technology Independent Program has a fairly high disposition, which is seen from the element of knowledge and understanding of the program as well as the commitment given to program implementation. This disposition is manifested by the existence of implementing teams who already have clear and adequate knowledge and understanding regarding the contents, aims and objectives of program implementation, are always ready to be deployed to the village to monitor the process of implementing the merdeka program such as the implementation of pretest and post-test to monitor the results of merdeka program implementation.

The above is in line with what was revealed by the Vice Rector 3 of the Sumbawa University of Technology, namely: *"To maintain the process of implementing the independence program, we use a team for the implementation of the merdeka program to go to each village to see the achievements so far. ., M.Sc .27 April 2021)"*.

This positive attitude of assessment then encourages the growth of awareness and commitment of the implementing teams to be able to carry out their respective functions and duties, full of compliance and responsibility in providing services to the community.

Bureueratic Structure

The organizational structure is the part in charge of implementing the policy. One of the most important structural aspects of any organization is the existence of standard operating procedures (SOPs). By using SOPs, implementers can optimize the available time and can function to uniform the actions of officials in complex and widespread organizations, so that it can lead to great flexibility and great similarity in the application of regulations [14]. Associated with the implementation of the Merdeka Program at the Sumbawa University of Technology, the implementers must comply with the existing SOPs, which are contained in the 2020 Village Project Pocket Book "Merdeka Builds Villages for Community Welfare". Research and Innovation Field.

The bureaucratic structure in the implementation of the merdeka program at the Sumbawa University of Technology is carried out in accordance with the concept created by the Vice Chancellor for Research and Innovation and coordinated with his subordinate elements or organizations, the Directorate of Community Service. Such coordination is needed to create good and harmonious cooperation conditions between various implementing parties so that program implementation can run towards the goals to be achieved.

Influent Factors in the Merdeka Program

One of the objectives of an merdeka program policy is to create a learning culture that is innovative, unfettered, and in accordance with the needs of higher education institutions, as well as being able to keep up

with changes and the need for link and match in the world of work. PTs are required to produce graduates who are able to adapt to the needs of employment in the current millennial era, thus requiring extensive knowledge and skills. There are various interests from all elements involved in the implementation of this program. To support the implementation of the Merdeka Program, local stakeholders and the active role of the target community groups must be supported so that the policies that have been formulated can be implemented or adhered to by the target community groups when the policy is implemented. As stated by Husnul Imtahan [4] in his journal that because only with the participation of the program recipient community, the results of this development will be in accordance with the aspirations and needs of the community. Therefore, one of the indicators of development success is the participation of the program recipient community.

Based on the findings of interviews from stakeholders, it can be concluded that several important factors that influence the implementation of the Merdeka Program are:

- a) There is full support from village heads in developing villages through the Merdeka Program so that village problems can easily be solved together. The village even asked for the merdeka program to continue in order to advance the village economy.
- b) The establishment of communication from the Sumbawa University of Technology with stakeholders, whether the communication is built through formal or non-formal forums so that they can maintain mutual coordination.
- c) Guaranteed budget for the implementation of the merdeka Program from the local government so that it can assist the implementation of the merdeka program in developing villages.
- d) There is a sense of ownership in developing the Sumbawa Regency area, this is proven by always socializing the merdeka program as well as stakeholders and the Sumbawa University of Technology jointly monitoring the implementation of the merdeka program in each of the assisted villages.
- e) The innovation and creativity of the Sumbawa University of Technology students in growing and designing village products to be used as the village's superior products in order to increase the income of the village community.

V. CONCLUSION

- a) The communication process carried out through coordination between the Sumbawa Technological University and stakeholders in the implementation of the merdeka program has been carried out quite clearly, effectively and efficiently through various meetings, both formal and informal meetings. With this communication, each part of the implementer can have the same perception and understanding of the goals, objectives and procedures of program implementation so as to facilitate each part in coordination. Even the portion of communication is the most important part in socializing the independence program.
- b) Human resources as implementers and physical resources in the form of supporting facilities for the implementation of the program are sufficient, both in terms of quantity and quality, so that they can positively support the implementation of the merdeka program. For funding resources, local government guarantees are sufficient in carrying out the independence program.
- c) The implementing team for the merdeka program for Warek 3 of the Sumbawa University of Technology has a fairly high disposition. This can be seen from the existence of the implementing teams who have had a high response in monitoring the implementation of the merdeka program in the form of conducting pretest and posttest on the process of implementing the merdeka program. So that the results achieved can be measured and find out what problems will be used as input in the next stage of the merdeka program.
- d) The bureaucratic structure consists of implementing organizations, in this case the Directorate of Community Service under the Deputy Chancellor 3 (Research and Innovation) who coordinate with each other in the implementation of the Merdeka Program. The action of the implementor in carrying out is in accordance with the SOP that has been set. The implementation team's compliance with the SOP is very important to support the mechanism for implementing the merdeka program so that it can run according to the provisions that have been set.

- e) The village as the target group provides positive support for the implementation of the Merdeka Program because the village heads in Sumbawa Regency consider that the merdeka program has provided great benefits in improving economic welfare for the community. By bringing up the potential and superior products of the community so that it elevates the image village from other villages.

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